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STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF QUALITIES OF A MULTICULTURAL PERSONALITY OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPIL IN A MULTI-ETHNIC ENVIRONMENT

P.A. Kudabayeva,

PhD, M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, (Kazakhstan, Taraz), e-mail: perizat_2003@gmail.com

G.K. Abdrakhman,

Candidate of philology, M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, (Kazakhstan, Taraz), e-mail: gulnar.abdrakhman@mail.ru

Abstract. *The prerequisites for the education of a multicultural personality are laid in preschool age and at the stage of a child's education in primary school. Concretization of the qualities that form the basis of a multicultural personality is possible from the perspective of an anthropological approach, in the context of consideration of the age and psychological characteristics of children of primary school age.*

Key words: *multicultural personality, multi-ethnic, educational environment.*

Children of primary school age are characterized by emotionality, heightened sensitivity, synchronicity to the experiences of another person. At the same time, they are characterized by such qualities as curiosity, quick reactions, enthusiasm for interesting and meaningful for them business. The most important social factors of a child's development affect him by virtue of his natural activity. As a rule, the activity of children of primary school age is expressed in actions and deeds. Because the social situation of children's development is characterized by a set of conditions that ensure their transition from preschool to school, children eagerly await adults' recognition of a new social status - that of a pupil - and prepare to master a new activity - learning. Games, which occupied all their free time in preschool age, are fading into the background. However, they do not disappear, but are preserved along with learning activities. This allows us to conclude that in the multi-ethnic educational environment of primary school there should be games and game situations.

The studies by I.A. Arabov, R.A. Akhmedkhanova, A.A. Tsakhaeva and others point out that in the younger school age the formation of the child's national identity

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continues, and there is a desire to tell the teacher about the traditions, culture, customs of the native family and ethnic community to which he or she belongs.

We understand national identity as one of the components of a person’s self-consciousness related to the realised belonging to a certain ethnic group or nation. It is not identical to the concepts of nationality or citizenship, although they may be factors that strongly influence it.

National identity is not a natural trait. It arises from an acquired awareness of a shared culture, history and language with a particular group of people. To this can be added a sense of belonging to a particular state, commitment to its state identity, national idea and state symbols. National identity can be multileveled and complex. Small peoples without statehood often have a national identity that combines a regional ethno-cultural identity with a broader national identity linked to the political nation and the state. The national identity of migrants can be defined both by their origin and their self-identification with the new state and its cultural environment. At certain stages of development, several projects of national identity may compete within one ethno-cultural group [1].

The idea of social situation of development emerged in the works of L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, L.I. Bozhovich, A.V. Zaporozhets, D.B. Elkonin and others. The separate history of each child, a representative of his/her family, is connected with the history and traditions of his/her contacts with others. The child’s awareness of belonging to his or her family and a certain ethnic community contributes to the formation of ethnic identity with compatriots and representatives of other nationalities. Through the ethnic group, children establish links with their relatives, accept, assimilate and adopt the stereotypes of behaviour, moral and everyday values and traditions of their people. In this way, they develop an orientation to the world around them, an understanding of other people, and an interest in their roots, in themselves, in close relatives and in the ethnic community [2].

Analyzing the formation of higher forms of human behavior, L.S. Vygotsky writes that the essence of education is identified with the history of development of human culture. Giving recommendations to educators, he writes about what a teacher should understand: “...entering the culture, the child not only takes something from it, assimilates something, inculcates something from outside, but the culture itself deeply processes the natural composition of the child’s behavior”.

L. Vygotsky introduced into the scientific turnover of psycho-pedagogical science the concept of “cultural age”, reflecting the degree of achievement in the

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child's ideological and cultural development. He was inclined to identify the child's personality with his cultural development, between worldview and socialisation [3].

The concept of ethnic identity is widely studied both in the works of foreign and domestic researchers. The formation of awareness of an individual's own ethnic identity was studied by one of the first Swiss scientists, J. Piaget. In his works he singles out the stages of ethnic identity formation at the conscious level, which occurs in children at a very early age. According to the research, the scientist comes to the conclusion that ethnic identity and national feelings are formed in a child from the age of 6-7 years. At the same time, the formation of the image of the Motherland in the child's consciousness and the formation of a sense of patriotism have a decisive influence [4].

In the studies of J. Piaget and E. Erikson it was established that ethnic identity goes through several stages of development, correlated with the age stages of human mental development. And if E. Erikson's concept is devoted to the crisis of adolescent identity, in his research J. Piaget analyzed the stages of development of ethnic characteristics during the period of primary school age: from 6 to 11 years old. He established three stages of ethnic identity formation associated with the stages of cognitive development: the stage of disparate ideas, the stage of identification with the family, the stage of realization of ethnicity and the development of the prerequisites of national identity [5].

At the first stage in 6-7 years old, the child acquires fragmentary, fragmentary, unsystematised knowledge about his/her ethnicity and ethnic features of people around him/her. This stage can be characterized as the stage of fragmentary identity, fragmented ideas about the ethnic peculiarities of others.

At the second stage, from the age of 8-9, the child is able to selectively identify himself with his ethnic group. Identification involves the immediate environment: parents, relatives, close friends. The basis for identification is the peculiarities of the native language, place of residence, and everyday traditions. Identification at this stage is selective and mediated by the child's immediate environment. Through relatives, he or she learns the ethnic features of himself or herself, his or her family and their difference from other ethnic features.

At the third stage, by the end of primary school age, ethnic identity is fully formed: the specificity of traditions, the uniqueness of the nation's history, and the peculiarities of everyday culture are realized. Thus, the third stage is the stage of full, but not completed identity. The child consciously defines his/her ethnicity and characterizes the main national features of his/her people, defines differences with

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representatives of other ethnic groups. However, it cannot be assumed that the process of identity formation is completed by the age of 11; it may be completed later.

Children’s realization of their national identity is greatly influenced by their living environment. An inter-ethnic environment gives a child more opportunities to acquire knowledge about the peculiarities of his or her own and other ethnic groups, develops communication skills and experience of interaction with representatives of other ethnic groups. A mono-ethnic environment narrows the opportunities for cultural familiarization with the traditions of other peoples and one’s own ethno-cultural achievements. A multi-ethnic educational environment creates conditions for the formation of the main qualities of a multicultural personality. Children living in environments with different ethnic cultural characteristics have the most pronounced ethnic identity, while those living among culturally close ethnic groups have blurred boundaries. The process of ethnic identification of primary school children is dialectical. On the one hand, self-identification is carried out; on the other hand, the group’s evaluation and acceptance of a child of another ethnicity is formed.

In modern studies reflecting ontogenetic features of students, it is noted that the leading types of activities are a meaning-forming factor in the formation of a multicultural personality. According to D. B. Elkonin’s concept, the development of a child’s ideas about himself and others largely depends on the degree of inclusion in the leading activity. It was noted above that the leading activity of primary school students is learning activity. However, despite the fact that learning activity comes to the fore, such activities as play, labor, and communication remain significant and important. They can act as pedagogical methods of propaedeutic work on the development of the main qualities of a multicultural personality in the polyethnic educational environment of primary schools.

The child, included in the system of various types of activities, has the opportunity to self-discovery and cognition of other people. Educational and cognitive activities are of particular importance in the education of a multicultural personality of a junior schoolchild. Self-knowledge, as well as knowledge and acceptance of the phenomena of the surrounding world and people of other nationalities, creates confidence that the surrounding world is harmonious and humane, and promotes self-affirmation and self-realization.

The most important type of activity that ensures the development of the basic qualities of a multicultural personality is labor activity. The use in the primary grades of self-care, household chores, duty work, work in the school grounds, manual labor,

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and the care of plants and animals promotes cooperation and responsibility, the formation of industriousness and mutual assistance among children of different nationalities.

The main link in the structure of the pedagogical system of education of preconditions of a multicultural personality at the stage of primary school age are the most important types of activity: cognition, communication, labor, play, etc. They develop motivation and values of a multicultural personality. They develop motivational-value, cognitive and communicative-behavioral spheres of a junior schoolchild’s personality. The undertaken characteristics of the age features of junior schoolchildren, as well as the analysis of the results of research on the problem of education of a multicultural personality, allow us to establish the presence of the main qualities and criteria of a multicultural personality (tab. 1).

Table 1. Structural components and criterion indicators of multicultural personality

Structural components	Criteria indicators
Communication tolerance	Wide multinational circle of communication; Following positive norms of communication with people of different nationalities; Performing joint activities with children of different nationalities; Willingness to listen to the interlocutor and conduct a dialogue
Social empathy	Recognizing the values of another ethnic group; Respect and interest in the partner’s language of communication; Understanding of the essence of interethnic peace and harmony, cultural diversity of the country and the world; Positive attitude and respect towards the communication partner, addressing him/her by name
Tolerance	Showing respect for the dignity of other ethnic groups; Willingness to recognize the possibility of different points of view and the right of everyone to have their own; Willingness to express one’s opinion and to argue one's point of view and assessment of events; Prevention and elimination of conflicts arising on the basis of ethnic and cultural contradictions
Humanity	Humane attitude to people and nature; Awareness of humanistic and democratic value orientations; Readiness for a positive perception and understanding of the life of the surrounding society
Emotional resilience	Respect for one’s own national identity and the identity of another person;

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	Ability to follow the basic traditions and rules established by the ethnic community; Willingness to overcome difficulties in relations with representatives of other ethnic communities
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The above allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. A multicultural personality is a person who perceives himself as a subject of the dialogue of cultures, has an active life position, has a developed sense of tolerance, emotional stability, capable of productive activity in a diverse society. A multicultural person is a person with a pronounced historical consciousness. It is historical consciousness that is the basis of both ethnic and national consciousness.

2. The qualities of the multicultural personality of a junior schoolboy are a complex new formation in the structure of the personality of a junior schoolboy who realizes himself as a subject of communication and joint activity with representatives of other ethnicities and cultures. They are laid down in preschool age and at the stage of a child's education in primary school.

3. The main task of multicultural education is to bring up a multicultural personality, i.e. to create conditions for identification of a person with his/her native culture and assimilation of other cultures, orientation to the dialogue of cultures, their mutual enrichment.

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